

IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION, HEALTH, AND PHYSICAL FITNESS

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ABSTRACT

Health and physical fitness have a vital role in the life of men from time immemorial. The progress of the Nation lies in the hands of the people, who are healthy and physically fit. Every individual should develop physical fitness for a happy and effective living. In order to get physical fitness one has to involve in physical activities.

***Keywords:** Fitness, hitched, manifestation, perfection, satisfaction, physical, health.*

INTRODUCTION

Physical education is the process by which changes in the individual are brought about through movement experiences. Physical education aims not only at physical development but is concerned with the education of the whole person through physical activity. It would be erroneous to believe that only physical responses are involved in physical education activities, the whole Organism interacts in any experience and this involves mental, emotional and social, as well as physical reactions. Such behaviour provides the physical educator with an exceptional opportunity to guide the responses of students so that valuable mental, emotional, social and physical learning's accrue.

Physical education should be a part of every individual's total education. Vigorous physical activity is a physiological necessity for optimum health and well-being yet it is a need, which is often poorly met, in our sedentary society. Through physical education a person can and should learn the satisfaction and joy of movement, exercise and activity. The individual can and should acquire adequate physical movement skills so that throughout life that person will seek physical activity and thus maintain muscle tone and cardiovascular Efficiency. Physical education means to maintain and extend endurance, strength and flexibility. It can be physically beneficial, socially acceptable means to release tension; but more than that, it can be a social participation in which one can grow to know one's self. An instructional program in physical education with the opportunities for some selection of sports, dance, conditioning, outdoor and recreational activities should be a part of the educational curriculum of every individual.

MEANING AND IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

The primary aim of physical education is physical fitness of the individual. The method can content in physical education to improve physical fitness are to be visualized. Physical education is a process through which an individual obtain optimal, physical, mental and social skills and fitness physical activity **Lumpkin (1986)**.

Physical education is a meaningful and worthwhile experience obtained through participation in physical activities that are physically wholesome mentally stimulating and satisfying and socially sound **William (1966)**.

Physical education is necessary because it will make all physically fit to healthy to stimulate and satisfying the mind to keep all the socially sound and to give leadership training. It is a must for youngster like students who like to have mental stimulation and satisfaction. There has been a keen awareness of the need for physical fitness on a nationwide basis.¹

EDUCATION AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION

“Body and mind should be driven like a pair of horses hitched to a shaft”.

- **Sathyanesan (1970)**

Thirunarayanan and Hariharan (1959) quoted Swami Vivekanandas definition “Education as the manifestation of perfection already in the man”. Education is drawn out the best in man through his, mind and spirit. Physical education is an educational process that has as its aim, the improvement of human performance through the medium of physical activities selection to realize this outcome. Physical education includes the acquisition and refinement of motor skills, the development and maintenance of fitness for optimal health and well-being the attainment of knowledge the growth of positive attitude towards physical activity **Bucher (1989)**

The education is taking place in three learning domains, cognitive affective and psychomotor, physical education contributes domains, social needs, trends and for force which influence the objective of education and also sport within a society as well within the educational process. Recent years have been marked by calls for educational reforms, specially revitalization and strengthening of educational processes. The nature of educational reform that are being implemented may have for reaching consequence on the conduct of physical educational programmes in schools and colleges **Bucher and other(1987)**

MEANING OF PHYSICAL FITNESS:

□ Physical fitness is the capacity to do work effectively with joy and pleasure. After the work is over, he still has sufficient capacity to do more work without any exertion. Moreover, his recovery must be faster

and quicker.

□ Physical fitness is related to work or task. It is a good physique. It is proper functioning of physiological system. The term physical fitness has wide meaning. It is more than the possession of strength, speed, endurance. The person who remains energetic, cheerful, and enthusiastic in doing his work is said to be physically fit.

□ It's level vary from person to person depending upon the nature of work, size, shape, structure, sex and age of an individual.

IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL FITNESS:

Following are the importance of physical fitness:

1. Harmonious Growth and development:

Physical fitness is a good factor for growth and development of body. It keeps our body stretch and active.

2. Personality development:

Physical fitness is helpful in making the look of a person more attractive. It can fill energy and healthy body.

3. Development of health:

It also be a cause of development of health also. If a person is physically fit he has more ability to perform activities, if a person is not a physically good he is not able to do work efficiently.

4. Boosts energy:

Physical fitness also facilitate to boosting up energy of a body.

5. Increases stamina:

If a person is physically fit, stamina also increases in a body.

6. Mental strength increase:

It is also a cause of increasing mental capabilities to do work easily.²

It is necessary for every individual to be physically fit to perform their daily work with ease and to take part in various activities effectively. Everyone should be fit enough through participation in physical activities to develop the different physical fitness components.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Physical activity and physical education are two terms that are often mistakenly used interchangeably. While there are inherent similarities and overlapping, there's one point that needs to be made clear physical education and physical activity are not synonymous.

Physical Activity

Recess is fantastic. It's a time for kids to run around and around with only their imaginations, a few swings

and a basketball hoop. It's what makes being a kid so great. This kind of fun counts for physical activity, not education. When kids are at home and head out to play freeze tag or red light green light, or when they head to dance practice, or when they chase lightning bugs around the yard, it also accounts for physical activity. It's important. It releases endorphins, builds muscle and bone density, and improves coordination. But physical activity does not complete the picture of good health for our children. Physical education contains physical activity, but it also contains a lot of other things that set up children for long-term health of the body, mind, and spirit.

Physical Education

According to the 2010 Shape of the Nation report conducted by the National Association for Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) and the American Heart Association, "Physical education is based on a sequence of learning ... [which] also includes health, nutrition, social responsibility, and the value of fitness throughout one's life." Unfortunately, the past few years have been unkind to those gym and health classes (collectively, PE) that were cut as a result of schools "teaching to the test." Math, science, and reading took precedent over PE time, which doesn't quite fit in to decreased budgets. The Shape of the Nation report continues: "Providing time for unstructured physical activity is not the same as providing instructional time for meeting the goals of quality physical education."³

NEED FOR FITNESS EDUCATION

Fitness education is a subcomponent of the total physical education program, focusing on helping students acquire knowledge and higher-order understanding of health-related physical fitness (the product), as well as habits of physical activity and other healthy lifestyles (the process) that lead to good health-related physical fitness, health and wellness. Although the term "fitness" is used in many ways, in this project, fitness education is defined as health-related fitness education. The following working definition of fitness is used to guide the development of IFFEPE: fitness education is the instructional and learning process of acquiring knowledge, skills and values; experiencing regular participation in physical activity; and promoting healthy nutrition choices to achieve life-enhancing health-related fitness.⁴

PHYSICAL FITNESS AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Physical activity involves any bodily movement such as walking to and from work, taking the stairs instead of elevators and escalators, gardening, and doing household chores. For inactive people, there's no doubt that increasing this sort of activity can reduce risk for disease and improve health. Exercise, however, is a type of physical activity that requires planned, structured, and repetitive bodily movement with the intent of improving or maintaining your physical fitness level. Exercise can be accomplished through activities such as cycling, dancing, walking, swimming, yoga, working out at the gym, or running, just to name a few.

Regular exercise, depending upon the kind, improves aerobic fitness, muscular strength, and flexibility.

Aerobic fitness is the ability of the body's cardiovascular system to supply energy during continuous physical activities such as biking and running. Studies show that this type of exercise provides many health benefits such as decreasing risk for heart disease, stroke, high blood pressure, type II diabetes and some cancers. The 2008 Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans state that most health benefits occur with at least 150 minutes/week of moderate-intensity aerobic activity. Examples of aerobic activities that would meet this recommendation include walking at a brisk pace, swimming, jogging, dancing, etc.

Muscular strength is the ability of the muscles to exert a force during an activity such as lifting weights. Muscle strengthening exercises involve using your muscles to work against a resistance such as your body weight, elastic bands or weights. The Physical Activity Guidelines recommend that adults participate in muscle strengthening exercises for all major muscles groups at least two days a week.

Bone strengthening exercise, or any weight-bearing activity that produces a force on the bone, is also important to overall health for children and adults. This force is usually produced by impact with the ground and results in bone growth in children and healthy maintenance of bone density in adults. Examples of bone strengthening activities include jumping, walking, jogging, and weight lifting exercises. As you can see, some exercises such as walking or jogging serve a dual purpose of strengthening our bones and our aerobic system.

Lastly, **flexibility** is the ability of the joints to move through a full range of motion. Stretching exercises can be an excellent way of increasing flexibility. While the 2008 Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans do not include specific recommendations for increasing flexibility, some individuals such as dancers and some athletes may need to include flexibility activities as part of their exercise regimen. The bottom line is that increasing your everyday physical activity and regularly participating in aerobic, muscle and bone strengthening exercises are all beneficial to your health and will improve your quality of life.

CONCLUSION

Physical activity is essential for the development of wholesome personality of a child which would depend upon the opportunities provided for wholesome development of the mental, physical, social and spiritual aspects. Hence a well-organized and properly administered physical education programme for school children is very essential. Physical activity throughout the ages has been acclaimed for health and recreation. It provided fun and enjoyment. It also provided youthful exuberance and the elderly care. Physical activity and movements are as old as human existence. It played numerous roles from struggle for existence to struggle for excellence.

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